

R O O T L I N K S

VISUAL GUIDELINES

LOGO GUIDELINES

Logo clear space

To maintain the logo's visibility and impact, it's important to always respect its minimum clear space. This protective area ensures that no other elements interfere with the logo or compete with it visually. The minimum distance that must be kept free of any text, images, or graphic elements around the logo is illustrated in the image.

The logo is provided with this clear space already built in, so you don't need to calculate it manually. Just make sure not to place anything within this area — the safe zone around the logo should always remain empty to ensure consistent and effective brand presentation.

Positive and negative variations

The logo is available in two versions: positive and negative. Both retain the original colors of the semicircles, but are adapted to ensure visibility on different backgrounds. The positive version is intended for use on white backgrounds,

while the negative version should be used exclusively on dark green backgrounds. This distinction ensures the logo remains clear, consistent, and visually effective in all applications.

Monochrome variations

A monochromatic version of the logo is also available for use on colored backgrounds. The three additional palette colors – pink, yellow, and light blue – can serve as backgrounds, provided the dark monochromatic logo is used to ensure

proper contrast. The white monochromatic version of the logo is reserved exclusively for use on black backgrounds, and only when printing limitations or technical constraints prevent the use of the standard versions.

Logo on images

The monochromatic version of the logo can also be used on photographic backgrounds. However, it's essential to ensure readability by placing the logo on areas of the image that are visually clean, with minimal detail and a relatively

flat background. Avoid positioning the logo over busy or complex sections of the image to maintain clarity and brand consistency.

COLOR PALETTE

Color palette

WHITE #FFFFFF	R255 G255 B255 C0 M0 Y0 K0	
GREEN #09282D	R4 G40 B45 C93 M61 Y58 K70	
YELLOW #E6E868	R230 G232 B204 C18 M0 Y71 K0	
PINK #F2CBD3	R242 G203 B211 C7 M40 Y17 K0	
BLUE #96C6D6	R150 G198 B214 C42 M10 Y15 K0	

Color accessibility combinations

Not all color combinations are suitable for accessibility. It's important to follow the **WCAG 2.1 guidelines**, which **ensure content is accessible to users with disabilities**.

Level AA provides sufficient contrast for most users, while Level AAA offers higher contrast for those with visual

impairments. Always consider these standards when choosing colors for the project's graphic materials. For AAA, the appropriate contrast ratio is 4.5:1. For AA, the appropriate contrast ratio is 3:1.

TYPOGRAPHY

Bitter

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Aa

REGULAR ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
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ITALIC ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789(!#€%&/.|'@,?;:)*

SEMIBOLD ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789(!#€%&/.|*'@,?;:)

Typographic hierarchy

HEADLINES
Always in all caps
Bitter Regular

HEADLINE
LOREM IPSUM

SUBHEADLINES
Bitter Regular

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Pellentesque vitae sem ut magna tristique dignissim.

PARAGRAPH
Bitter Regular

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Pellentesque vitae sem ut magna tristique dignissim. Aenean nec lectus eu nunc viverra facilisis. Morbi ac justo at odio faucibus fermentum. Nulla facilisi. Sed ac malesuada nulla, sed sodales urna.

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